

**Comorbidity patterns associated with severe COVID-19 outcomes:
a cohort study based on the UK Biobank**

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Supplementary Methods

1. Comorbidity network analysis

Step 1: The initial step involves pre-selecting disease 1 (D1) and disease 2 (D2) pairs with considerable comorbidity strength. Start by constructing all possible disease pairs using medical conditions selected from the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) codes. For each pair of diseases, create sub-cohorts by excluding individuals who have the corresponding medical condition or a history of related medical conditions. If either of the medical conditions in a disease pair is sex-specific, further restrict the sub-cohort to either males or females. Then, if the co-occurrence of these two medical conditions was experienced by at least 1.0% of the individuals in the sub-cohort, relative risk (RR) and Φ -correlation were calculated using the following formulas [1]:

$$RR_{ij} = \frac{C_{ij}N_{ij}}{C_i C_j}$$

$$\Phi_{ij} = \frac{C_{ij}N_{ij} - C_i C_j}{\sqrt{C_i C_j (N_{ij} - C_i)(N_{ij} - C_j)}}$$

Where C_{ij} is the number of individuals affected by both medical conditions, N_{ij} is the number of individuals in the sub-cohort, C_i is the number of individuals affected by D1, and C_j is the number of individuals affected by D2. For both RR and Φ -correlation measures, the significance of RR=0 and $\Phi=0$ can be determined using a z-test. The corresponding z-score for RR and Φ -correlation can be calculated using the following formulas [1, 2]:

$$z_{ij}^{RR} = \frac{\ln(RR_{ij})}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{C_{ij}} - \frac{1}{N_{ij}} + \frac{1}{C_i C_j / N_{ij}} - \frac{1}{N_{ij}}}}$$

$$z_{ij}^{\Phi} = \frac{\Phi_{ij} \sqrt{\max(C_i, C_j) - 2}}{\sqrt{1 - \Phi_{ij}^2}}$$

P-values were then calculated using the z-score and adjusted for the issue of multiple testing. Disease pairs with significant comorbidity strength were identified by considering a significant relative risk (RR) >1.5 and Φ -correlation >0 (i.e., q-value <0.05 for both measures). These eligible disease pairs would proceed to the next step.

Step 2: For each pre-selected disease pair, unconditional logistic regression models were used to further verify the comorbidity associations between D1 and D2 in the corresponding sub-cohort, while adjusting for household income, BMI, smoking status, drinking status, and Townsend deprivation index. D1↔D2 disease pairs with confirmed comorbidity association (i.e., OR >1.0 and q-value <0.05 in the unconditional logistic regression) were used to construct comorbidity network construction. Finally, we applied Louvain method to partition the networks into several modules with high intrinsic networks. The Louvain method is based on the following assumption: the network should have nodes (medical conditions) that are strongly interconnected. In the context of the disease comorbidity network, this assumption is quite palatable.

2. Module-based comorbidity index calculation

First, a node importance ranking method was employed to assess the significance of disease nodes within our comorbidity network. Subsequently, the weight of each disease was determined by multiplying its importance within the corresponding module by the odds ratio (OR) of the association between the respective module and severe COVID-19. The comorbidity index of an individual is defined as the sum of the disease weights associated with each disease they suffer from. The formulas for the calculations are as follows [3]:

$$L_{vi} = k_i + \sum_{v_j \in \Gamma_j} \frac{(k_i - p - 1)(k_j - p - 1)}{\frac{p}{2} + 1} \cdot \frac{k_i - 1}{k_i + k_j - 2}$$

$$\text{Comorbidity index}_m = \sum_{m \in G} (\beta_m \cdot \sum_{i \in m} \frac{L_{vi}}{S_m})$$

$$S_m = \sum_{i \in m} (L_{vi})$$

Where Γ_j is the set of neighbors for v_i , k_i and k_j are the degrees of v_i and v_j , and p is the number of triangles formed where one edge connects v_i and v_j .

3. Machine learning for prediction models

We randomly split the dataset into training and test datasets, and used the training dataset for developing the comorbidity index and fitting the model. Support Vector Machine (SVM) and eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) algorithms were employed to construct prediction models that incorporated age and sex as additional covariates. We applied 10-fold cross-validation with grid-search on the training dataset to tune the hyperparameters in both SVM and XGBoost algorithms. Hyperparameters used for training SVM models: class_weight, 1:7; kernel, linear; C, 10; gamma, 0.1. Hyperparameters used for training XGBoost models: max_depth=6, learning_rate=0.05, n_estimators=100, booster='gbtree', gamma=0, min_child_weight=1, subsample=1, colsample_bytree=1, reg_alpha=0, reg_lambda=1. The Akaike information criterion (AIC) and Bayesian information criterion (BIC) as evaluation metrics were calculated using the following formulas [4,5]:

$$AIC = 2k + n \ln(MSE)$$

$$BIC = k \ln(n) + n \ln(MSE)$$

Where k is the number of parameters in the fitted model, n is the number of observations, and MSE is mean square error.

References:

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4. Akaike H. Citation Classic - a New Look at the Statistical-Model Identification. Cc/Eng Tech Appl Sci 1981(51):22-22.
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Supplementary Table 1 COVID-19 identification in primary care

Code	Preferred term description
Y20d1	SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) RNA (ribonucleic acid) detection result positive
Y20cf	Suspected coronavirus disease 19 caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (situation)
Y23ec	SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) IgG detection result positive
Y23f0	SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) IgM detection result positive
A795.	Coronavirus infection
A7y00	Coronavirus as cause of dis classified to other chapters
Y20fa	Coronavirus disease 19 caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (disorder)
Y210b	Infection of upper respiratory tract caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (disorder)
Y211c	Serotype 2019-nCoV (novel coronavirus)
Y228e	Coronavirus disease 19 caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 confirmed using clinical diagnostic criteria (situation)
Y20d1	SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) RNA (ribonucleic acid) detection result positive
Y20fb	Encephalopathy caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (disorder)
Y20fc	Gastroenteritis caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (disorder)
Y20fe	Myocarditis caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (disorder)
Y20ff	Otitis media caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (disorder)
Y210a	Pneumonia caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (disorder)
Y23fd	Cardiomyopathy caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (disorder)
XaaNq	Suspected coronavirus infection
Y20cf	Suspected coronavirus disease 19 caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (situation)
Y22b7	Patient reported having already had Covid-19 in the recent past (not tested)
Y22b8	Patient reported having already had Covid-19 in the recent past (tested)
Y23f2	SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) total immunoglobulin arbitrary concentration in serum
Y244e	Arbitrary concentration of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 immunoglobulin A in serum (observable entity)
Y23f1	SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) IgM arbitrary concentration in serum
Y246f	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 immunoglobulin A detected (finding)
Y23ed	SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) IgG arbitrary concentration in serum
Y212f	Antibody to 2019-nCoV (novel coronavirus)
Y23ec	SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) IgG detection result positive
Y23f0	SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) IgM detection result positive
Y240a	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 immunoglobulin M qualitative existence in specimen (observable entity)
Y23f2	SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) total immunoglobulin arbitrary concentration in serum
Y23ed	SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) IgG arbitrary concentration in

	serum
Y23f1	SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) IgM arbitrary concentration in serum
Y244e	Arbitrary concentration of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 immunoglobulin A in serum (observable entity)
Y23ff	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 immunoglobulin G qualitative existence in specimen (observable entity)
Y23e9	Has immunity to SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2)
Y246f	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 immunoglobulin A detected (finding)
Y210c	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 serology (observable entity)
AyuDC	[X]Coronavirus infection, unspecified
X73IE	Coronavirus
X73IF	Human coronavirus
Y213a	Antigen of 2019-nCoV (novel coronavirus)
Y228d	Coronavirus disease 19 caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 confirmed by laboratory test (situation)
Y240b	SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) RNA (ribonucleic acid) qualitative existence in specimen
Y23f7	SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2) detection result positive
441590008	Pneumonia caused by Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (disorder)
700217006	Suspected coronavirus infection
713084008	Pneumonia caused by Human coronavirus (disorder)
720294006	Severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus IgM
720293000	Immunoglobulin G antibody to Severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus
840533007	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2
840539006	Disease caused by 2019 novel coronavirus (disorder)
840544004	Suspected disease caused by 2019 novel coronavirus (situation)
840536004	Antigen of Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2
866151004	Lymphocytopenia due to COVID-19
866152006	Thrombocytopenia due to 2019 novel coronavirus
870588003	Sepsis due to disease caused by COVID-19
870589006	Acute kidney injury due to disease caused by COVID-19
870590002	Acute hypoxemic respiratory failure due to disease caused by COVID-19
870591003	Rhabdomyolysis due to disease caused by Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (disorder)
870362002	Immunoglobulin M antibody to Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2
870361009	Immunoglobulin G antibody to Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2
870362002	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 IgM
897034005	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 antibody test positive
1017214008	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 viremia
1119302008	Acute COVID-19
1119303003	Post-acute COVID-19 (disorder)
1119304009	Chronic COVID-19 syndrome
1119343008	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 mRNA
1300721000000109	Coronavirus disease 19 caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 confirmed by laboratory test
1321301000000101	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 ribonucleic acid qualitative existence in

specimen

132278100000102 Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 antigen detection result positive

Supplementary Table 2 The theoretical and observed infection rate in the study population

Age group	No. of cases/population in England	Infection rate in England (per 100,000)	Population in the study	Theoretical no. of cases in the study population	Observed no. of cases in the study population
50-54	604,870/4,252,628	14220	15,978	2,273	2,063
55-59	501,982/4,195,969	11960	53,506	6,400	6,144
60-64	345,090/3,672,954	9400	60,544	5,692	5,553
65-69	222,614/3,025,304	7360	69,292	5,100	4,863
70-74	178,603/2,739,789	6520	92,427	6,027	5,096
75-79	130,252/2,406,517	5410	91,280	4,939	4,961
80+	197,093/2,434,531	8100	37,893	3,070	2,254
Total	2,180,504/22,727,692	9590	420,920	33,501	30,914
Theoretical infection rate in the UKB participants: 9,590					
Observed infection rate in the UKB participants: 7,340					

Supplementary Table 3 List of 115 GBD codes used in the current study

Disease name	Category	Corresponding ICD10 codes
HIV/AIDS	Infectious diseases	B20-B23.8, B24-B24.0, B97.81, C46-C46.52, C46.7-C46.9, F02.4
Sexually transmitted infections excluding HIV	Infectious diseases	A50-A60.9, A63-A64.0, B63, I98.0, K67.0-K67.2, M73.0-M73.8, N70-N71.9, N73-N74, N74.2-N74.8
Tuberculosis	Infectious diseases	A10-A14, A15-A18.89, A19-A19.9, B90-B90.9, K67.3, K93.0, M49.0, N74.0-N74.1
Lower respiratory infections	Infectious diseases	A48.1, A70, B96.0-B96.1, B97.21, B97.4-B97.6, J09-J18.2, J18.8-J18.9, J19.6-J22.9, J85.1, J91.0
Upper respiratory infections	Infectious diseases	J00-J06.9, J36-J36.0
Otitis media	Infectious diseases	H65-H70.93
Diarrheal disease	Infectious diseases	A00-A00.9, A02-A02.0, A02.8-A07, A07.2-A07.4, A08-A08.8, A09, K52.1
Typhoid and paratyphoid	Infectious diseases	A01-A01.4
Meningitis	Infectious diseases	A39-A39.9, A87-A87.9, D86.81, G00-G03.9, G06-G09.9
Encephalitis	Infectious diseases	A83-A85.2, A85.8-A86.0, B94.1, F07.1, G04-G05.8
Diphtheria	Infectious diseases	A36-A36.9
Whooping cough	Infectious diseases	A37-A37.91
Tetanus	Infectious diseases	A33-A35.0
Measles	Infectious diseases	B05-B05.9
Varicella and herpes zoster	Infectious diseases	B01-B02.9
Acute hepatitis	Infectious diseases	B15-B19.9, B94.2
Protein-energy malnutrition	Infectious diseases	E40-E46.9, E64.0
Iodine deficiency	Infectious diseases	E00-E02
Vitamin A deficiency	Infectious diseases	E50-E50.9, E64.1
Dietary iron deficiency	Infectious diseases	D50-D50.9
Lip and oral cavity cancer	Neoplasms	C00-C07, C08-C08.9
Nasopharynx cancer	Neoplasms	C11-C11.9
Esophageal cancer	Neoplasms	C15-C15.9
Stomach cancer	Neoplasms	C16-C16.9
Colon and rectum cancer	Neoplasms	C18-C19.0, C20, C21-C21.8
Liver cancer	Neoplasms	C22-C22.4, C22.7-C22.9
Gallbladder and biliary tract cancer	Neoplasms	C23, C24-C24.9
Pancreatic cancer	Neoplasms	C25-C25.9
Larynx cancer	Neoplasms	C32-C32.9
Tracheal, bronchus, and lung cancer	Neoplasms	C33, C34-C34.92
Malignant skin melanoma	Neoplasms	C43-C43.9
Non-melanoma skin cancer	Neoplasms	C44.01-C44.99

Breast cancer	Neoplasms	C50-C50.629, C50.8-C50.929
Cervical cancer	Neoplasms	C53-C53.9
Uterine cancer	Neoplasms	C54-C54.3, C54.8-C54.9
Ovarian cancer	Neoplasms	C56-C56.2, C56.9
Prostate cancer	Neoplasms	C61-C61.9
Testicular cancer	Neoplasms	C62-C62.92
Kidney cancer	Neoplasms	C64-C64.2, C64.9-C65.9
Bladder cancer	Neoplasms	C67-C67.9
Brain and central nervous diseases cancer	Neoplasms	C70-C70.1, C70.9-C72.9
Thyroid cancer	Neoplasms	C73
Mesothelioma	Neoplasms	C45-C45.2, C45.7, C45.9
Hodgkin lymphoma	Neoplasms	C81-C81.49, C81.7-C81.79, C81.9-C81.99
Non-Hodgkin lymphoma	Neoplasms	C82-C85.29, C85.7-C86.6, C96-C96.9
Multiple myeloma	Neoplasms	C88-C90.32
Leukemia	Neoplasms	C91-C93.7, C93.9-C95.2, C95.7-C95.92
Rheumatic heart disease	Circulatory system diseases	I01-I01.9, I02.0, I05-I09.9
Ischemic heart disease	Circulatory system diseases	I20-I21.6, I21.9-I25.9
Ischemic stroke	Circulatory system diseases	G45-G46.8, I63-I63.9, I65-I66.9, I67.2-I67.848, I69.3-I69.4
Intracerebral hemorrhage	Circulatory system diseases	I61-I62, I62.9, I69.0-I69.298
Subarachnoid hemorrhage	Circulatory system diseases	I60-I60.9, I67.0-I67.1
Hypertensive heart disease	Circulatory system diseases	I11-I11.2, I11.9
Non-rheumatic valvular heart diseases	Circulatory system diseases	I34-I37.9
Cardiomyopathy and myocarditis	Circulatory system diseases	B33.2-B33.20, B33.22-B33.24, D86.85, I40-I41.8, I42-I43.8, I51.4-I51.6
Atrial fibrillation and flutter	Circulatory system diseases	I48-I48.92
Peripheral artery disease	Circulatory system diseases	I70.2-I70.92, I73-I73.9
Endocarditis	Circulatory system diseases	B33.21, I33-I33.9, I38-I38.0, I39-I39.9
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	Respiratory system diseases	J41-J42.4, J43-J44.9
Pneumoconiosis	Respiratory system diseases	J60-J65.0, J92.0
Asthma	Respiratory system diseases	J45-J46.0
Interstitial lung diseases and pulmonary sarcoidosis	Respiratory system diseases	D86-D86.2, D86.9, J84-J84.9
Cirrhosis and other chronic liver disease	Digestive system diseases	I85-I85.9, I98.2, K70-K71, K71.3-K72, K72.1-K75, K75.2, K75.4-K76.2, K76.4-K77.8
Upper digestive disease	Digestive system diseases	K21-K21.9, K22.7-K22.719, K25-K30
Peptic ulcer disease	Digestive system diseases	K25-K28.9
Gastritis and duodenitis	Digestive system diseases	K29-K29.91
Gastroesophageal reflux diseases	Digestive system diseases	K21-K21.9, K22.7-K22.719
Appendicitis	Digestive system diseases	K35-K37.9
Paralytic ileus and intestinal obstruction	Digestive system diseases	K56-K56.9
Inguinal, femoral, and abdominal	Digestive system diseases	K40-K42.9, K44-K46.9

hernia		
Inflammatory bowel diseases	Digestive system diseases	K50-K51.319, K51.5-K52, K52.8-K52.9
Vascular intestinal disorders	Digestive system diseases	K55-K55.9
Gallbladder and biliary diseases	Digestive system diseases	K80-K80.81, K81-K83.9, K87-K87.1
Pancreatitis	Digestive system diseases	K85-K86.9
Alzheimer's diseases and other dementias	Neurological system diseases	F00-F02.0, F02.8-F03.91, F06.2, G30-G31.1, G31.8-G32.89
Parkinson's disease	Neurological system diseases	F02.3, G20-G20.9
Idiopathic epilepsy	Neurological system diseases	G40-G41.9
Multiple sclerosis	Neurological system diseases	G35-G35.0
Headache disorders	Neurological system diseases	G43-G44.89
Schizophrenia	Mental disorders	F20-F20.9, F25-F25.9
Depressive disorders	Mental disorders	F32-F33.9, F34.1
Bipolar disorder	Mental disorders	F30-F31.9, F34.0
Anxiety disorders	Mental disorders	F40-F44.9, F93-F93.2
Eating disorders	Mental disorders	F50-F50.9
Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder	Mental disorders	F90-F90.9
Conduct disorder	Mental disorders	F91-F92.9
Idiopathic developmental intellectual disability	Mental disorders	F70-F79.9
Alcohol use disorders	Mental disorders	E24.4, F10-F10.99, G31.2, G62.1
Drug use disorders	Mental disorders	F11-F19.99
Diabetes mellitus	Endocrine diseases	E08-E08.11, E08.3-E08.9, E10-E10.11, E10.3-E11.1, E11.3-E12.1, E12.3-E13.11, E13.3-E14.1, E14.3-E14.9
CKD (induced by DM)	Genitourinary system diseases	E10.2-E10.29, E11.2-E11.29
CKD (induced by HYPERTENSION)	Genitourinary system diseases	I12-I13.9
CKD	Genitourinary system diseases	N02-N08.8
Acute glomerulonephritis	Genitourinary system diseases	N00-N01.9
Dermatitis	Dermatologic condition	L20-L23.2, L23.4-L27, L27.2-L27.9, L30-L30.2, L30.5-L30.9
Psoriasis	Dermatologic condition	L40-L41.9
Bacterial skin disease	Dermatologic condition	A46-A46.0, A66-A67.3, A67.9, I89.1-I89.8, L00-L05.92, L08-L08.9, L30.3-L30.4, L88, L97-L98.499, M72.5-M72.6, N49.2-N49.3
Scabies	Dermatologic condition	B86
Fungal skin disease	Dermatologic condition	B35-B36.9
Viral skin disease	Dermatologic condition	B07-B09
Acne vulgaris	Dermatologic condition	L70-L70.9
Alopecia areata	Dermatologic condition	L63-L63.9
Pruritus	Dermatologic condition	L29-L29.9
Urticaria	Dermatologic condition	L50-L50.9
Decubitus ulcer	Dermatologic condition	L89-L89.95
Blindness and vision loss	Sensory system diseases	H25-H28.8, H31-H36.8, H40-H40.9, H42-H42.8, H46-H54.9

Glaucoma	Sensory system diseases	H40-H40.9,H42-H42.8
Cataract	Sensory system diseases	H25-H26.9,H28-H28.8
Age-related macular degeneration	Sensory system diseases	H35.3-H35.389
Refraction disorders	Sensory system diseases	H52-H52.7
Age-related and other hearing loss	Sensory system diseases	H71-H75.83, H80-H80.93, H83-H83.93, H90-H91, H91.1-H91.93, H94-H94.8
Rheumatoid arthritis	Musculoskeletal system diseases	M05-M05.9, M08-M09.8
Osteoarthritis	Musculoskeletal system diseases	M16-M18.9
Gout	Musculoskeletal system diseases	M10-M10.19, M10.3-M10.9, M1A00X0-M1A9XX1
		G54.4, M47.015-M47.019, M47.15-M47.18, M47.25-M47.28, M47.815-M47.818, M47.896-M47.899, M48.05-M48.08, M48.16-M48.19, M48.25-M48.27, M48.35-M48.38, M48.45-M48.48, M48.55-M48.58, M49.85-M49.88, M51.05-M51.07, M51.15-M51.17, M51.25-M51.27, M51.35-M51.37, M51.45-M51.47, M51.85-M51.87, M53.3, M53.85-M53.88, M54.05-M54.09, M54.15-M54.18, M54.3-M54.5, M99.03-M99.04, M99.13-M99.14, M99.23-M99.24, M99.33-M99.34, M99.43-M99.44, M99.53-M99.54, M99.63-M99.64, M99.73-M99.74, M99.83-M99.84
Low back pain	Musculoskeletal system diseases	

Supplementary Table 4 Diagnostic codes for the identification of severe COVID-19

Category	ICD-10 code	Disease name	
I. Certain infectious and parasitic diseases	A00-A09	Intestinal infectious diseases	
	A15-A19	Tuberculosis	
	A20-A28	Certain zoonotic bacterial diseases	
	A30-A49	Other bacterial diseases	
	A50-A64	Infections with a predominantly sexual mode of transmission	
	A65-A69	Other spirochetal diseases	
	A70-A74	Other diseases caused by chlamydia	
	A75-A79	Rickettsioses	
	A80-A89	Viral infections of the central nervous system	
	A92-A99	Arthropod-borne viral fevers and viral hemorrhagic fevers	
	B00-B09	Viral infections characterized by skin and mucous membrane lesions	
	B15-B19	Viral hepatitis	
	B20-B24	Human immunodeficiency virus [HIV] disease	
	B25-B34	Other viral diseases	
	B35-B49	Mycoses	
	B50-B64	Protozoal diseases	
	B65-B83	Helminthiases	
	B85-B89	Pediculosis, acariasis and other infestations	
	B90-B94	Sequelae of infectious and parasitic diseases	
	B95-B98	Bacterial, viral and other infectious agents	
	B99-B99	Other infectious diseases	
	II. Neoplasms	C00-C97	Malignant neoplasms
		D00-D09	In situ neoplasms
D10-D36		Benign neoplasms	
D37-D48		Neoplasms of uncertain or unknown behaviour	
III. Diseases of the blood and blood-forming organs and certain disorders involving the immune mechanism	D50-D53	Nutritional anaemias	
	D55-D59	Haemolytic anaemias	
	D60-D64	Aplastic and other anaemias	
	D65-D69	Coagulation defects, purpura and other haemorrhagic conditions	
	D70-D77	Other diseases of blood and blood-forming organs	
IV. Endocrine, nutritional and metabolic diseases	D80-D89	Certain disorders involving the immune mechanism	
	E00-E07	Disorders of thyroid gland	
	E10-E14	Diabetes mellitus	
	E15-E16	Other disorders of glucose regulation and pancreatic internal secretion	
	E20-E35	Disorders of other endocrine glands	
	E40-E46	Malnutrition	
	E50-E64	Other nutritional deficiencies	
	E65-E68	Obesity and other hyperalimentation	

	E70-E90	Metabolic disorders
V. Mental and behavioral disorders	F00-F09	Organic, including symptomatic, mental disorders
	F10-F19	Mental and behavioral disorders due to psychoactive substance use
	F20-F29	Schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders
	F30-F39	Mood [affective] disorders
	F40-F48	Neurotic, stress-related and somatoform disorders
	F50-F59	Behavioral syndromes associated with physiological disturbances and physical factors
	F60-F69	Disorders of adult personality and behavior
	F70-F79	Mental retardation
	F80-F89	Disorders of psychological development
	F90-F98	Behavioral and emotional disorders with onset usually occurring in childhood and adolescence
	F99-F99	Unspecified mental disorder
VI. Diseases of the nervous system	G00-G09	Inflammatory diseases of the central nervous system
	G10-G14	Systemic atrophies primarily affecting the central nervous system
	G20-G26	Extrapyramidal and movement disorders
	G30-G32	Other degenerative diseases of the nervous system
	G35-G37	Demyelinating diseases of the central nervous system
	G40-G47	Episodic and paroxysmal disorders
	G50-G59	Nerve, nerve root and plexus disorders
	G60-G64	Polyneuropathies and other disorders of the peripheral nervous system
	G70-G73	Diseases of myoneural junction and muscle
	G80-G83	Cerebral palsy and other paralytic syndromes
G90-G99	Other disorders of the nervous system	
VII. Diseases of the eye and adnexa	H00-H06	Disorders of eyelid, lacrimal system and orbit
	H10-H13	Disorders of conjunctiva
	H15-H22	Disorders of sclera, cornea, iris and ciliary body
	H25-H28	Disorders of lens
	H30-H36	Disorders of choroid and retina
	H40-H42	Glaucoma
	H43-H45	Disorders of vitreous body and globe
	H46-H48	Disorders of optic nerve and visual pathways
	H49-H52	Disorders of ocular muscles, binocular movement, accommodation and refraction
	H53-H54	Visual disturbances and blindness
	H55-H59	Other disorders of eye and adnexa
VIII. Diseases of the ear and mastoid process	H60-H62	Diseases of external ear
	H65-H75	Diseases of middle ear and mastoid
	H80-H83	Diseases of inner ear
	H90-H95	Other disorders of ear
IX. Diseases of the circulatory system	I00-I02	Acute rheumatic fever
	I05-I09	Chronic rheumatic heart diseases

	I10-I15	Hypertensive diseases
	I20-I25	Ischaemic heart diseases
	I26-I28	Pulmonary heart disease and diseases of pulmonary circulation
	I30-I52	Other forms of heart disease
	I60-I69	Cerebrovascular diseases
	I70-I79	Diseases of arteries, arterioles and capillaries
	I80-I89	Diseases of veins, lymphatic vessels and lymph nodes, not elsewhere classified
	I95-I99	Other and unspecified disorders of the circulatory system
X. Diseases of the respiratory system	J00-J06	Acute upper respiratory infections
	J09-J18	Influenza and pneumonia
	J20-J22	Other acute lower respiratory infections
	J30-J39	Other diseases of upper respiratory tract
	J40-J47	Chronic lower respiratory diseases
	J60-J70	Lung diseases due to external agents
	J80-J84	Other respiratory diseases principally affecting the interstitium
	J85-J86	Suppurative and necrotic conditions of lower respiratory tract
	J90-J94	Other diseases of pleura
	J95-J99	Other diseases of the respiratory system
XI. Diseases of the digestive system	K00-K14	Diseases of oral cavity, salivary glands and jaws
	K20-K31	Diseases of oesophagus, stomach and duodenum
	K35-K38	Diseases of appendix
	K40-K46	Hernia
	K50-K52	Noninfective enteritis and colitis
	K55-K64	Other diseases of intestines
	K65-K67	Diseases of peritoneum
	K70-K77	Diseases of liver
	K80-K87	Disorders of gallbladder, biliary tract and pancreas
	K90-K93	Other diseases of the digestive system
XII. Diseases of the skin and subcutaneous tissue	L00-L08	Infections of the skin and subcutaneous tissue
	L10-L14	Bullous disorders
	L20-L30	Dermatitis and eczema
	L40-L45	Papulosquamous disorders
	L50-L54	Urticaria and erythema
	L55-L59	Radiation-related disorders of the skin and subcutaneous tissue
	L60-L75	Disorders of skin appendages
	L80-L99	Other disorders of the skin and subcutaneous tissue
XIII. Diseases of the musculoskeletal system and connective tissue	M00-M25	Arthropathies
	M30-M36	Systemic connective tissue disorders
	M40-M54	Dorsopathies
	M60-M79	Soft tissue disorders

	M80-M94	Osteopathies and chondropathies
	M95-M99	Other disorders of the musculoskeletal system and connective tissue
XIV. Diseases of the genitourinary system	N00-N08	Glomerular diseases
	N10-N16	Renal tubulo-interstitial diseases
	N17-N19	Renal failure
	N20-N23	Urolithiasis
	N25-N29	Other disorders of kidney and ureter
	N30-N39	Other diseases of urinary system
	N40-N51	Diseases of male genital organs
	N60-N64	Disorders of breast
	N70-N77	Inflammatory diseases of female pelvic organs
	N80-N98	Noninflammatory disorders of female genital tract
	N99-N99	Other disorders of the genitourinary system

Supplementary Table 5 COVID-19 vaccination identification in primary care

Code	Preferred term description
Y210d	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 vaccination (procedure)
Y211e	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 vaccination declined (situation)
Y210d	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 vaccination (procedure)
Y20fd	High priority for severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 vaccination (finding)
840534001	COVID-19 vaccination
1119305005	COVID-19 antigen vaccine
1119349007	COVID-19 mRNA vaccine
1119350007	COVID-19 mRNA vaccination
1142180003	COVID-19 vaccine adverse reaction
1142181004	Adverse reaction to COVID-19 mRNA vaccine
1142182006	Adverse reaction to COVID-19 antigen vaccine
1144997007	First COVID-19 mRNA immunization
1144998002	Second COVID-19 mRNA immunization
1145003007	Hypersensitivity to COVID-19 mRNA vaccine
1145031003	COVID-19 vaccine declined
1145032005	COVID-19 mRNA vaccine declined
1145033000	COVID-19 antigen vaccine declined
1145034006	Second dose of COVID-19 mRNA vaccine declined
1156256003	COVID-19 vaccine adverse reaction
1156257007	COVID-19 immunization
1156270003	COVID-19 vaccine declined
1157106007	COVID-19 non-replicating viral vector vaccine adverse reaction
1157107003	COVID-19 non-replicating viral vector vaccination
1157108008	Second COVID-19 non-replicating viral vector vaccination
1157118003	COVID-19 non-replicating viral vector vaccine declined
1157120000	Second dose of COVID-19 non-replicating viral vector vaccine declined
1162643001	COVID-19 recombinant spike protein antigen vaccine
1162644007	COVID-19 recombinant spike protein antigen vaccine adverse reaction
1162645008	COVID-19 recombinant spike protein antigen vaccination
1162646009	Second dose of COVID-19 recombinant spike protein antigen vaccination
1162649002	COVID-19 recombinant spike protein antigen vaccine declined
1162650002	Second dose of COVID-19 recombinant spike protein antigen vaccine declined
1324681000000101	Administration of first dose of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 vaccine
1324721000000108	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 vaccination dose declined
1324741000000101	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 vaccination first dose declined
1324811000000107	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 immunization course declined
1324691000000104	Administration of second dose of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 vaccine
1324751000000103	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 vaccination second dose declined
1363791000000101	Administration of fourth dose of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 vaccine
1363831000000108	Administration of fifth dose of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 vaccine
1363861000000103	Administration of third dose of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 vaccine
1362651000000105	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 protection maintenance course refused
1324721000000108	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 vaccination dose declined
1324811000000107	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 immunization course declined

Supplementary Table 6 The ICD-10 codes for the identification of severe COVID-19 case

ICD-10 code	Disease name	No. of cases
U07	COVID-19	2534
I20-I25	Ischemic heart diseases	149
E11-E14	Diabetes mellitus	132
J44-J47	Chronic lower respiratory diseases	128
I60-I69	Cerebrovascular diseases	94
I30-I52	Other forms of heart disease	77
F00-F09	Organic, including symptomatic, mental disorders	64
J09-J18	Influenza and pneumonia	57
I10-I15	Hypertensive diseases	53
K70-K77	Diseases of liver	44
N17-N19	Renal failure	42
C76-C80	Malignant neoplasms of ill-defined, secondary and unspecified sites	38
A30-A49	Other bacterial diseases	36
C15-C26	Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs	34
I70-I79	Diseases of arteries, arterioles and capillaries	32
E65-E68	Obesity and other hyperalimentation	32
G35-G37	Demyelinating diseases of the central nervous system	23
C69-C72	Malignant neoplasms of eye, brain and other parts of central nervous system	23
N30-N39	Other diseases of urinary system	22
G20-G26	Extrapyramidal and movement disorders	21
I26-I28	Pulmonary heart disease and diseases of pulmonary circulation	21
E00-E07	Disorders of thyroid gland	21
D37-D48	Neoplasms of uncertain or unknown behavior	18
J20-J22	Other acute lower respiratory infections	18
C50	Malignant neoplasm of breast	17
C73-C75	Malignant neoplasms of thyroid and other endocrine glands	17
C81-C96	Malignant neoplasms, stated or presumed to be primary, of lymphoid, hematopoietic and related tissue	15
C45-C49	Malignant neoplasms of mesothelial and soft tissue	15
J85-J86	Suppurative and necrotic conditions of lower respiratory tract	15
G30-G32	Other degenerative diseases of the nervous system	14
C30-C39	Malignant neoplasms of respiratory and intrathoracic organs	14
N10-N16	Renal tubulo-interstitial diseases	13
I80-I89	Diseases of veins, lymphatic vessels and lymph nodes, not elsewhere classified	12
D60-D64	Aplastic and other anemias	12
J80-J84	Other respiratory diseases principally affecting the interstitium	11
C00-C14	Malignant neoplasms of lip, oral cavity and pharynx	11
K20-K31	Diseases of esophagus, stomach and duodenum	10
C51-C58	Malignant neoplasms of female genital organs	9
C60-C63	Malignant neoplasms of male genital organs	9
D70-D77	Other diseases of blood and blood-forming organs	9
C64-C68	Malignant neoplasms of urinary tract	8
G10-G14	Systemic atrophies primarily affecting the central nervous system	8

C43-C44	Melanoma and other malignant neoplasms of skin	8
K80-K87	Disorders of gallbladder, biliary tract and pancreas	7
A80-A89	Viral infections of the central nervous system	7
G60-G64	Polyneuropathies and other disorders of the peripheral nervous system	7
K55-K64	Other diseases of intestines	5
J60-J69	Lung diseases due to external agents	2
J90-J94	Other diseases of pleura	1
K65-K67	Diseases of peritoneum	1

Supplementary Table 7 The association between each individual disease and the risk of severe COVID-19

Disease name	Subordinate disease module	OR^a	95%CI
Glaucoma	Sensory disease module	1.180	0.955-1.451
Cataract	Sensory disease module	1.478	1.295-1.684
Age-related macular degeneration	Sensory disease module	1.243	0.935-1.641
Refraction disorders	Sensory disease module	1.210	0.877-1.649
Dietary iron deficiency	Digestive disease module	1.351	1.134-1.606
Cirrhosis and other chronic liver diseases	Digestive disease module	1.681	1.383-2.038
Gastritis and duodenitis	Digestive disease module	1.102	0.975-1.244
Gastroesophageal reflux disease	Digestive disease module	1.123	0.999-1.261
Inguinal, femoral, and abdominal hernia	Digestive disease module	1.212	1.089-1.347
Gallbladder and biliary diseases	Digestive disease module	1.308	1.093-1.561
Diabetes mellitus	Cardiometabolic disease module	1.919	1.627-2.259
CKD (induced by DM)	Cardiometabolic disease module	1.526	1.313-1.771
CKD (induced by hypertension)	Cardiometabolic disease module	1.279	1.139-1.434
Rheumatoid arthritis	Cardiometabolic disease module	1.064	0.809-1.388
Osteoarthritis	Cardiometabolic disease module	0.912	0.816-1.019
Low back pain	Cardiometabolic disease module	0.937	0.845-1.038
Gout	Cardiometabolic disease module	1.123	0.982-1.282
Hypertensive heart disease	Cardiometabolic disease module	1.224	1.091-1.372
Atrial fibrillation and flutter	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	1.932	1.682-2.217
Peripheral artery disease	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	1.523	1.264-1.831
Ischemic heart disease	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	1.271	1.142-1.413
Ischemic stroke	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	1.897	1.624-2.214
Non-rheumatic valvular heart disease	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	1.492	1.215-1.827
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	1.585	1.376-1.824
Pneumoconiosis	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	1.099	0.811-1.478
Asthma	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	1.201	1.067-1.35
Rheumatic heart disease	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	1.438	1.160-1.777
Decubitus ulcer	Intestinal disease module	2.473	1.807-3.391
Diarrheal diseases	Intestinal disease module	1.017	0.896-1.151
Diphtheria	Intestinal disease module	0.933	0.787-1.103
Inflammatory bowel disease	Intestinal disease module	1.197	1.024-1.395
Lower respiratory infections	Intestinal disease module	1.175	1.059-1.303
Depressive disorders	Psychological related disease module	1.388	1.213-1.586
Alcohol use disorders	Psychological related disease module	1.467	1.226-1.751
Drug use disorders	Psychological related disease module	1.367	1.185-1.575
Dermatitis	Psychological related disease module	1.048	0.937-1.171
Urticaria	Psychological related disease module	1.073	0.853-1.340
Psoriasis	Psychological related disease module	1.137	0.924-1.392
Fungal skin diseases	Psychological related disease module	0.854	0.746-0.976
Pruritus	Psychological related disease module	0.901	0.737-1.095
Age-related and other hearing loss	Infectious disease module	0.982	0.866-1.111
Typhoid and paratyphoid	Infectious disease module	0.846	0.630-1.122
Bacterial skin diseases	Infectious disease module	0.974	0.879-1.078
Anxiety disorders	Infectious disease module	0.996	0.893-1.110

Idiopathic epilepsy	Infectious disease module	1.213	1.029-1.428
Headache disorders	Infectious disease module	0.939	0.814-1.082
Viral skin diseases	Infectious disease module	1.012	0.832-1.227
Sexually transmitted infections excluding HIV	Infectious disease module	0.877	0.765-1.003
Tuberculosis	Infectious disease module	0.848	0.720-0.995
Upper respiratory infections	Infectious disease module	0.911	0.822-1.010T
Otitis media	Infectious disease module	0.894	0.772-1.034

^aAdjusted for age, sex, annual household income, TDI, BMI, smoking status, drinking status, and the disease status of other modules

Supplementary Table 8 The node importance of diseases in seven comorbidity modules

Disease	Module	Node importance
Cataract	Age-related eye disease module	5.00
Diphtheria	Gastrointestinal disease module	3.39
Asthma	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	3.14
Atrial fibrillation and flutter	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	2.50
Ischemic heart disease	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	2.48
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	2.25
Lower respiratory infections	Gastrointestinal disease module	1.93
Rheumatic heart disease	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	1.72
Non-rheumatic valvular heart disease	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	1.67
Age-related macular degeneration	Age-related eye disease module	1.67
Refraction disorders	Age-related eye disease module	1.67
Glaucoma	Age-related eye disease module	1.67
Gallbladder and biliary diseases	Digestive disease module	1.60
Inguinal, femoral, and abdominal hernia	Digestive disease module	1.60
Gastroesophageal reflux disease	Digestive disease module	1.60
Gastritis and duodenitis	Digestive disease module	1.60
Dermatitis	Mental and skin disorder module	1.58
Rheumatoid arthritis	Cardiometabolic disease module	1.56
Pruritus	Mental and skin disorder module	1.51
Inflammatory bowel disease	Gastrointestinal disease module	1.38
Depressive disorders	Mental and skin disorder module	1.35
Gout	Cardiometabolic disease module	1.29
Cirrhosis and other chronic liver diseases	Digestive disease module	1.28
Dietary iron deficiency	Digestive disease module	1.28
Hypertensive heart disease	Cardiometabolic disease module	1.22
CKD (induced by HYPERTENSION)	Cardiometabolic disease module	1.21
Ischemic stroke	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	0.99
CKD (induced by DM)	Cardiometabolic disease module	0.84
Diarrheal diseases	Gastrointestinal disease module	0.83
Alcohol use disorders	Mental and skin disorder module	0.67
Drug use disorders	Mental and skin disorder module	0.67
Fungal skin diseases	Mental and skin disorder module	0.67
Diabetes mellitus	Cardiometabolic disease module	0.60
Decubitus ulcer	Gastrointestinal disease module	0.42
Osteoarthritis	Cardiometabolic disease module	0.40
Viral skin diseases	Infectious and neuropsychiatric disease module	0.37
Psoriasis	Mental and skin disorder module	0.34
Urticaria	Mental and skin disorder module	0.34
Peripheral artery disease	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	0.33
Pneumoconiosis	Circulatory and respiratory disease module	0.33
Sexually transmitted infections excluding HIV	Infectious and neuropsychiatric disease module	0.32

Tuberculosis	Infectious and neuropsychiatric disease module	0.32
Age-related and other hearing loss	Infectious and neuropsychiatric disease module	0.30
Anxiety disorders	Infectious and neuropsychiatric disease module	0.30
Idiopathic epilepsy	Infectious and neuropsychiatric disease module	0.27
Headache disorders	Infectious and neuropsychiatric disease module	0.22
Low back pain	Cardiometabolic disease module	0.20
Typhoid and paratyphoid	Infectious and neuropsychiatric disease module	0.15
Upper respiratory infections	Infectious and neuropsychiatric disease module	0.07
Bacterial skin diseases	Infectious and neuropsychiatric disease module	0.03
Otitis media	Infectious and neuropsychiatric disease module	0.03

Supplementary Table 9 Comparison of comorbidity indices in predicting risk of severe COVID-19

Algorithm	Comorbidity index	Primary evaluation metric	Secondary evaluation metric	
		AUC	AIC	BIC
XGBoost	CCI	0.714	-14131	-14111
	16-comorbidity based index	0.714	-14060	-13989
	Full module-based comorbidity index	0.779	-14531	-14511
	Simplified module-based comorbidity indices (No. of diseases for calculating comorbidity index)			
	40	0.775	-14515	-14495
	35	0.778	-14565	-14545
	30	0.772	-14498	-14478
	25	0.774	-14502	-14482
	20	0.763	-14457	-14437
	15	0.762	-14409	-14381
SVM	CCI	0.679	-6197	-6177
	16-comorbidity based index	0.678	-6089	-5967
	Full module-based comorbidity index	0.710	-7675	-7655
	Simplified module-based comorbidity indices (No. of diseases for calculating comorbidity index)			
	40	0.709	-7623	-7603
	35	0.708	-7696	-7676
	30	0.707	-7576	-7555
	25	0.704	-7531	-7511
	20	0.703	-7299	-7279
	15	0.701	-7183	-7162

AIC, Akaike Information Criterion; AUC, the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve; BIC, Bayesian Information Criterion; CCI, Charlson Comorbidity Index; SVM, Support Vector Machine; XGBoost, EXtreme Gradient Boosting. 16-comorbidity based index was reported in previous literature, including 16 diseases. The full module-based comorbidity index included all 51 diseases.

Supplementary Figure 1 Flowchart of the study population selection

^bThe first COVID-19 case was confirmed on 31 January 2020 in the UK.

Supplementary Figure 2 Sex-specific associations between comorbidity modules and severe COVID-19.

ORs (95%CI) were derived from fully adjusted logistic models (adjusted for age, Townsend deprivation index, annual household income, BMI, smoking status, drinking status, and disease status of other modules). The interaction between comorbidity modules and sex was evaluated by including the interaction term in the logistic models.

* $P < .05$.

Supplementary Figure 3 Association between comorbidity modules and severe COVID-19, stratified by vaccination status at diagnosis.

ORs (95%CI) were derived from fully adjusted logistic models (adjusted for age, sex, Townsend deprivation index, annual household income, BMI, smoking status, drinking status, and disease status of other modules). The interaction between comorbidity modules and vaccination status was evaluated by including the interaction term in the logistic models.

* $P < .05$.

Supplementary Figure 4 Association between comorbidity modules and severe COVID-19, stratified by time of last vaccination dose at diagnosis.

ORs (95%CI) were derived from fully adjusted logistic models (adjusted for age, sex, Townsend deprivation index, annual household income, BMI, smoking status, drinking status, and disease status of other modules).

Supplementary Figure 5 Association between comorbidity modules and severe COVID-19 stratified by different waves of the pandemic.

ORs (95%CI) were derived from fully adjusted logistic models (adjusted for age, sex, Townsend deprivation index, annual household income, BMI, smoking status, drinking status, and disease status of other modules). The interaction between comorbidity modules and different waves was evaluated by including the interaction term in the logistic models.

* $P < .05$.

Supplementary Figure 6 Flow chart of constructing the predictive model

AIC, Akaike Information Criterion; AUC, the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve; BIC, Bayesian Information Criterion; CCI, Charlson Comorbidity Index. ^o16 comorbidities reported in previous literature, including coronary artery disease, heart failure, atrial fibrillation, T1DM, T2DM, hypertension, asthma, COPD, cancer, dementia, depression, anxiety, psychosis, bipolar, cognitive impairment, and stroke.